

The Euphresco network and you

Euphresco network is interested in establishing links with organisations from all over the world whose mission is to define, fund or manage research programmes in the phytosanitary area. Such organisations are:

- programme owners: ministries and regional authorities defining research programmes
- programme managers: research funding agencies managing research programmes.

If you work for such an organisation and you are interested in joining the network, contact Euphresco!

Euphresco is also interested in collecting information on phytosanitary research projects in order to map the scientific panorama of the international research area.

If you know about phytosanitary research projects, or if you have expertise in the domain, please contact Euphresco.

2022 Euphresco network

Shqipëria Albania, الجزائر Algeria, Australia, Österreich Austria, Azərbaycan Azerbaijan, Беларусь Belarus, België Belgique Belgium, Босна и Херцеговина Bosnia and Herzegovina, България Bulgaria, Сав International, Canada, СИЕАМ-Bari, Hrvatska Croatia, Κύπρος Cyprus, Česká republika Czech Republic, Danmark Denmark, Eesti Estonia, Suomi Finland, France, Sak'art'velo Georgia, Deutschland Germany, Ελλάς Greece, Guernsey, Magyarország Hungary, Éire Ireland, ישראל Israel, Italia Italy, 日本国 Japan, Jersey, ندرألا Jordan, Казахстан Kazakhstan, Korea 대한민국, Кыргызстан Kyrgyzstan, Latvija Latvia, Lietuva Lithuania, Lëtzebuerg Luxembourg, Македонија Republic of Macedonia, Malta, Mexico, Moldova, Crna Gora Montenegro, برغمل Morocco, Aotea-roa New Zealand, Nederland Netherlands, Norge Norway, Polska Poland, Portugal, Romania, Россия Russian Federation, Србија Serbia, Slovensko Slovakia, Slovenija, España Spain, Sverige Sweden, Schweiz Switzerland, سنوت Tunisia, Türkiye Turkey, Україна Ukraine, United Kingdom, United States of America, Ўзбекистон Uzbekistan.

A network to enhance research coordination and facilitate international collaboration in the phytosanitary area

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